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THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation. *This article covers the reforms carried out in the development of the system of preschool education in our country, the issues of formation of children's knowledge when conducting training through innovative technologies in teaching educators, the peculiarities of the formation of historical ideas and knowledge in them, the study of the links between objects and phenomena methodology for the formation and development of.*

Key words: *innovative technology, innovation, knowledge, competence, method, Society, idea, integrative communication, creative thinking, project Technology, Information, Technology, "teacher portfolio".*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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Аннотация. *В данной статье освещаются проводимые в нашей стране реформы в развитии системы дошкольного образования, вопросы формирования знаний детей при обучении с помощью инновационных технологий обучения воспитанников, особенности формирования у них исторических идей и знаний, изучение связей между объектами и явлениями, методика формирования и развития основных понятий в сфере общества.*

Ключевые слова: *инновационная технология, инновация, знания, компетенция, метод, общество, идея, интегративная коммуникация, креативное мышление, технология проекта, информация, технология, "портфолио учителя".*

Introduction. Today, a preschool educational institution is a complex system that seeks to improve, develop, seeks new opportunities, creates the necessary conditions for meeting the needs of the child, family, society, creates conditions for the creative, professional activities of teachers who meet the most modern requirements. The introduction of innovations into the educational process is not just, it is not an indifferent attitude to the creative search for effective forms of work with children, it is time-consuming. In the implementation of a new system of education in our republic, the need for education reform of our Prezident has become an urgent task. The main focus was on improving educational systems on the basis of democratic and humanitarian principles, raising its material and technical base to the level of requirements of the time and period and strengthening the educational potential of Uzbekistan [1].

Also, the creation of conditions for achieving a new quality of education in the concept of modernization of preschool education is called the most important area of activity of educational institutions. It largely depends on how effectively innovations are mastered, which contribute to qualitative changes in the functioning of educational institutions. Currently, almost every preschool institution is included in the field of innovative activities. When it is said that preschool institutions work in a development mode, it means that they are engaged in innovation.

Analysis of thematic literature (Literature review). Methods and technologies of systematic analysis of pedagogical competency of future educators on the basis of innovative technologies K.Duncker, O. Thomas, M.Glozier has analyzed. Russian scientists I.V.Robert, P.V.Sisoyevs were studied in scientific research work related to the problems of systematic analysis of professional competence [2].

Research Methodology (Research Methodology). New educational programs have been created that allow you to ensure the variability of the educational process, aimed at new types, profiles and types of preschool educational institutions, the individuality of the child and the requirements of his family. Each pedagogical team has the right to innovative activities. Since children are the object of any pedagogical initiative, the teaching staff must undertake certain obligations for the preparation and organization of innovations.

Then, when there is a need to solve some problem, when a conflict arises between desire and the real result, the need for innovation arises. The development of general educational practices will help to demonstrate the creative, innovative potential of all employees in the preschool education system. In this situation, professional competence based on the personal and professional development of teachers and managers is especially important.

The philosophical encyclopedic Dictionary defines development as directed, natural and necessary changes. Based on the achievements of Science and the needs of society, innovative organizers make the design, start and support of the educational renewal process more effective.

Innovative activity is a special type of pedagogical activity. Innovation (innovation) — socially-psychologically — the creation and implementation of various innovations that bring about significant changes in social practice. Consequently, changes in the developing preschool educational institution are not accidental, but guided by the laws and aimed at achieving specific goals[3].

The goals and objectives of innovations are based, on the one hand, on a careful analysis of the current situation in the kindergarten, and on the other hand, on its development forecasts. There are the following different reasons for innovation: 1. The need to actively seek ways to solve existing problems in preschool education. 2. The desire of pedagogical communities to improve the quality of services provided to the population, make them more diverse and thereby preserve kindergartens. 3. Imitating other preschools, the intuitive idea of teachers that innovation improves the functioning of the entire team. 4. The desire to realize the knowledge gained by recent graduates of pedagogical universities, students of advanced training courses. 5. The constant dissatisfaction of some teachers with the results achieved, the firm intention to improve them. 6. The growing demands of individual groups of parents.

Analysis of the existing practice in the activities of preschool educational institutions working in an innovative mode has identified a number of problems: 1. Lack of scientific and methodological support for innovative processes; 2. Lack of consistency and integrity of the pedagogical innovations being implemented; 3. Regulatory legal regulation of innovative activities of preschool educational institutions; 4. The need to look for fundamentally new forms of interaction between scientific centers and innovation centers.

Often the question arises in teachers: where to start an innovative activity, what will be its final result? The algorithm of the innovation process is the same as any pedagogical activity: 1. Identifying the area of problematic education, advancing the goal of renewal (first of all, attention is paid to the relevance and importance of the problem) 2. Theoretical justification of an innovative idea, search for research methods, monitoring procedures). 3. Experiment. 4. Identification of defects, identification of methods for eliminating defects. 5. The next test (summing up the results, their presentation, dissemination of pedagogical experience).

The position and creative potential of teachers, active participation, one of the most important factors in the introduction of innovative ideas into the activities of a

preschool educational institution. Modern pedagogical technologies in preschool education are aimed at implementing federal state educational standards of preschool education. A fundamentally important aspect of pedagogical technology is the position of the child in the educational process, the attitude of adults towards the child. Its purpose is to contribute to the formation of the child as a person [6].

Among the modern educational technologies that are being introduced in a preschool educational institution are the following: - health technologies; - project activities technologies; - research activity technology; -ICT; - personality-oriented technologies; - educator portfolio technology; - gaming technology; - TRIZ technology; - Mnemonics. - Health technologies [3].

Health-saving pedagogical technologies include all aspects of the influence of the teacher on the health of the child at different levels — information, psychological, bioenergy. Ensuring the preservation and reproduction of children's health under the guidance of medical personnel in accordance with sanitary requirements and standards using medical and preventive, medical equipment: - technologies for organizing monitoring the health of preschool children; - control of children's nutrition, preventive measures, the formation of a health environment.

Each group has "health" centers (stand tips for parents, file cabinets of open games, sports equipment for independent activities of Children, "Health" folders containing information about the individual development of each child of the group) [5].

All this work should be carried out all day long and in every possible way with the participation of a medical officer and teachers: teachers, music director, teachers of speech therapists, teacher of physical education, teacher-psychologist.

Innovative technologies of project activities. Purpose: to develop and enrich social and personal experience by introducing children into the sphere of interpersonal interaction. The result of the use of technology: The use of project activities strengthens the cognitive motivation of children. In the process of project implementation, training becomes a process of conscious active search, application of new knowledge, strengthens the skill of using one's own experience, improves the ability to solve not only educational, but also educational problems. Children develop the skills and competencies they lack, creativity and communication skills, thus allowing it to be successful [4].

Technology for preparing children for the digital world. Work with teachers and parents is carried out in the following cases: - network connection; - Use of Internet Information Resources; - electronic tips on the institution's website; - the use of multimedia presentations.

As a result of the use of information and computer technologies in working with parents: - exchange information with colleagues via email, network professional teams, conversations, participation in on-line conferences; - training in distance learning courses; - search the necessary information materials on sites; - presentations are created to prepare for joint activities of teachers with their parents. -the opportunity to advise parents, teachers will be developed, taking advantage of the possibilities of the internet.

As a result of the use of information and computer technologies in the creation of a methodological system, teachers achieve the following: - access to storage, editing and access to large amounts of data; - electronic registration of reports and current documents; - use the internet network for self-education (electronic textbooks, finding articles on the desired topic). - creation, copying, Editing, reproduction of stimulating material for educational activities; - creating your own email address, blog, page, which gives you the opportunity to disseminate your pedagogical experience to the pedagogical community.

Innovational technology "teacher portfolio". In this technology, a successful teacher is studied an educator with modern innovative educational technologies, a high level of education and professional qualifications, able to predict the final result. The portfolio allows you to take into account the results achieved by the teacher in various types of activities and is an alternative form of assessment of the teacher's professional skills and effectiveness.

Analysis and Results (Analysis and results). By the integrated organization of innovative methods in the formation of skills for the application of innovative technologies in the educational process in future educators, - gets the result of children's activities; - adequately evaluates its activities, criticizes; - the ability to reflect its activities is developed; - characterizes the manifestation of perseverance, hard work through moral and volitional components on the basis of the established goal.

Conclusions and suggestions (Conclusion/Recommendations). In place of the conclusion, it can be said that each educator is given a certain degree of opportunity in children with indicators of understanding, systematization, generalization, creative transformation through the use of innovative technologies. The fact that children expand the volume of information about the world when it comes to kindergarten gives results in the use of techniques that will become effective material in the development of personality. Conditions are created when conducting reproductive activities, especially when the educator uses innovative teaching methods, provides children with various tasks for understanding and creative activities, organizes communicative and activity communication, and at the same time minimizes the elements of discussion.

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